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THE FUTURE OF CONTINUING ENGINEERING EDUCATION IN THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION AND PERSONALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The pace of introduction of new technology and thus continuous change in skill needs at workplaces, especially for the engineers, has increased. While digitization induced changes in manufacturing, construction and supply chain sectors may not be felt the same in every sector, this will be hard to escape. Both young and experienced engineers will experience the change, and the need to continuously assess and close the skills gap will arise. How will we, the continuing engineering educators and administrators will respond to it?

Prepared for engineering educators and administrators, this SEFI workshop has shed light on the future of continuing engineering education as we go through exponentially shortened time frames of technological revolution and in very recent time, in an unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

As rapid technological advances continue to transform the world of work, education systems play a critical role in preparing the global workforce of the future. Today, with the emergence of unpredictable global risks, such as the COVID-19 crisis, the educational models of higher education and continuing education institutions must be flexibly adapted to equip workers with the necessary tools to mitigate skills mismatches and identify viable models of quality education. Education in the Fourth Industrial Revolution can be modeled with the following four skills and four learning characteristics of high-quality learning as Education 4.0 Framework [1], as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Skills and learning characteristics of high-quality learning as Education 4.0 Framework [1]

Skills	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Global citizenship skills 2. Innovation and creativity skills 3. Technology skills 4. Interpersonal skills
Learning Characteristics	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Personalized and self-paced learning 2. Accessible and inclusive learning 3. Collaborative learning 4. Student-driven learning

The 21st century featured irreversible transformations that generated substantial changes in workforce development. International organizations including the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and World Economic Forum (WEF), in their pre-2020 reports, presented the situation as a global challenge: “meeting new demands requires focusing on the nature of future work and on the skills of the workforce to perform adequately those works” [2,3].

1.2 Workshop Focus

Traditionally, professional engineers and technologists have practiced a structured path for advancement in career, thus continuous professional development for those engineers has followed structured curriculum and pathway. However, during Industry 4.0, an era of digitalization – artificial intelligence, robotic process automation, data analytics, and blockchain --, does it look the same? Or, during the yet to arrive Industry 5.0, which is predicted to be the era of personalization and focus on humans and machine cooperation, how will the path of continuous professional development of the professional engineer look like? Will the engineers ever stop learning? Will they continuously have to reskill to cope with the ever-changing technology-based workplace or simply upskill to move forward?

As we are experiencing the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, we are asking ourselves, what knowledge, and skills that the industry will need in the post-pandemic world? Will it radically change from pre-pandemic need? Will the industry change so rapidly over the next few years that the engineers will need to reskill and upskill themselves continuously? Will academia be able to prepare the students for a life of continuous learning?

At the 2019 Annual SEFI Conference, the Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning Special Interest Group started preliminary conversation, followed by a hybrid meeting with both face-to-face and online attendees. The group wanted to evaluate the current and future work scenario, the change required in engineering education to accommodate the work scenario and whether there would learning communities needed to foster such changes.

However, there was no pandemic at that time. After the pandemic started, the situation changed and through virtual connection, the workshop was conducted at SEFI 2020.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Before the Workshop

Before the workshop, the participants were requested to read several web-based, freely available articles and international reports focused on the future of work and learning, as cited in the References [4-8].

The presenters also did a thorough investigation of engineering jobs in the market. There was no dearth of jobs for blockchain engineers or robotic process automation quality assurance engineer. It was also evident that the advent in artificial intelligence created jobs such as machine learning engineers. The presenters decided to share this information with the workshop participants.

2.2 During the Workshop

This workshop aimed to gather practitioners in the field of lifelong learning in engineering to brainstorm several paths for closing the obvious skills gap, rapid curriculum development, and deployment via accessible formats, flexible learning modes and paths, assessment, learning outcome evaluation and recognition, accreditation, and personalization.

The workshop participants critically assessed:

- the skills that the industry will require from the engineers in entry level and later
- how the industry and academia collaboratively can develop continuing engineering education curriculum to address such needs, and

- how the industry and academia collaboratively can prepare the students for a lifetime of learning.

2020 – The year of Coronavirus COVID-19 posed more challenges to overcome: work from, remote teaching and learning, factory job elimination, rapid digitization in all sectors and new types of skillsets in jobs. Change had happened at faster rate than anyone had thought.

The triggers questions to invigorate the thought process of the participants are shown in in Figure 1.

- What knowledge and skills that the industry will need in the post-pandemic world?
- Will it radically change from pre-pandemic need?
- Will the industry change so rapidly over the next few years that the engineers will need to reskill and upskill themselves continuously?
- Will academia be able to prepare the students for a life of continuous learning?

Figure 1. Trigger questions for the participants

Figure 2. Group discussion and brainstorming at the breakout rooms

The 75-minute virtual workshop was divided into four sections:

1. Presentation on the current situation of work and learning and triggering questions, shown in Figure 1. [Main Virtual Room]

2. Brainstorming discussions in two groups (as shown in Figure 2) on the possibilities during Industry 4.0 Digitization and possibilities during Industry 5.0 Personalization [Breakout Virtual Rooms].
3. Presentations on the future of work and learning [Main Virtual Room]
4. A list of work to do by the participants, as the workshop outcomes were summarized. [Main Virtual Room]

3 RESULTS

At the end of the workshop, participants experienced the following learning outcomes:

- A thorough knowledge of the current and future scenario of work for engineers
- how engineering education will need to incorporate a lifetime of learning mindset
- a framework developed by the participants themselves on how continuing engineering education learning communities will shape in the future while remaining agile in nature.

By answering the questions shown in Figures 1 and 2, we got preliminary ideas on how to proceed:

- Reinforce continuous training and upskilling in newer technologies such as Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, Robotic Process Automation, Blockchain-Based Operations, Services and Products Design and Simulations in undergraduate, graduate, and professional engineering education curricula.
- Reinforce the role of the educator as facilitator of the students so that they continue to “learning to learn” for the future work.

From a brief review of the documents that were available to the participants before the workshop, and the comments that emerged in the group discussion and brainstorming session, some relevant aspects could be obtained that had the consensus of the participants. Regarding how to build skills at “*speed & scale*”, we understand the importance of:

- Relate the business goals directly with the skills that are planned to be built, considering the planning of the workforce as an ongoing process.
- Include everyone -employees and employers / students and teachers- to create a culture of learning.
- Continuously measure and evaluate the relationship between learning and digital transformation goals.
- Do not forget the formal training, to teach people How to Learn.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The workshop participants agreed to highlight the following aspects as the most important related to the future of Continuing Education in Engineering:

With regard to Global Citizenship: raising awareness about the world in general and the active role that we must play in the global community;
With respect to collaborative learning: require the active collaboration and commitment of all colleagues and an approach that reflects the needs of future work; and
Finally, with respect to Innovation and Creativity Skills: include complex problem solving, analytical thinking, and ethical use of emerging technologies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] World Economic Forum. Schools of the future. Defining New Models of Education for the Fourth Industrial Revolution. World Economic Forum, Geneva, Switzerland, 2020.
- [2] K. Howells. The future of education and skills: education 2030: the future we want, 2018.
- [3] World Economic Forum Boston Consulting Group (BCG). Towards a reskilling revolution: a future of jobs for all. World Economic Forum, Geneva, Switzerland, 2018.
- [4] Bughin, J. Hazan, E., Lund, S., Dahlstrom, P., Weisinger, A. and Subramaniam, A. (2018), 'Skill shift: Automation and the future of the workforce'. McKinsey Global Institute. Retrieved from: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/future-of-work/skill-shift-automation-and-the-future-of-the-workforce> (accessed 22 April 2020).
- [5] Schwab, K., (2017), *The Fourth Industrial Revolution*. New York, NY: Crown Business, all pages.
- [6] Schwartz, J., Hartfield, S., Jones, R. and Anderson S., (2019), 'Redefining work, workforces and workplaces'. Deloitte Insights. Retrieved from: www2.deloitte.com/insights/us/en/focus/technology-and-the-future-of-work/redefining-work-workforces-workplaces.html (accessed 22 April 2020).
- [7] Marais, H., and Ntsoane, M., (2020), 'How the COVID-19 crisis is impacting the Future of Work? Deloitte Webinar Insights', retrieved from: https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/za/Documents/human-capital/Deloitte_How-Covid-impacts-the-FoW-Webinar-April-2020.pdf (accessed 1 August 2020)
- [8] Baier, J., Barybkina, E., Beauchene, V., Goel S., Lovich, D. and Lyle, E. (2020), 'Why You Need a New Approach to Learning'. Boston Consulting Group. Retrieved from: <https://www.bcg.com/en-gb/publications/2020/why-you-need-new-approach-learning> (accessed 1 August 2020)